

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS AND PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY OF RABI SORGHUM IN AMRAVATI DISTRICT

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Abstract

The present study entitled "Economic Analysis of Cost, Returns, and Resource Use Efficiency of Rabi Sorghum in Amravati District" was conducted during 2024-25 to analyze the cost structure, profitability, and resource use efficiency of sorghum cultivation. Amravati district of Maharashtra was purposively selected due to its significant area under rabi sorghum. Three tehsils Dharni, Chikhaldara, and Dhamangaon Rly. were selected, and from each, two villages were chosen randomly, making a total of 120 sample farmers categorized into small, medium, and large groups. The cost and return analysis were carried out using standard cost concepts (Cost A₁ to Cost C₃), and Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) was employed to estimate technical, allocative, and economic efficiencies. The results revealed that the average size of landholding was 1.91 ha. The overall per hectare cost of cultivation was ₹53,153.08 at Cost C₃, with an average gross return of ₹62,168.03 and a cost of production of ₹2,419.98 per quintal. Medium farmers achieved the highest profitability, followed by large and small farmers. The study found that hired human labour and machine labour were the major cost components. DEA results indicated varying levels of efficiency across farm sizes, suggesting potential for improved input utilization. The study concludes that enhancing resource management and optimizing input use can substantially increase the profitability and efficiency of rabi sorghum cultivation in the region.

Keywords: Rabi sorghum, cost and returns, profitability, DEA, resource use efficiency, Amravati district.

Introduction

Sorghum is the world's fifth-most important crop after rice, wheat, maize and barley. It is scientifically known as *Sorghum bicolor* L. belongs to Gramineae family and is popularly known as 'Jowar' in India. Among other millets, a large size is referred to as a 'Great millet'. It is also known as the "King of Millets". Sorghum is a major and important food grain in our country. Sorghum is the best alternative for extreme weather conditions and well suited to regions.

World sorghum production in 2024-25 is estimated as United states being largest producer of sorghum produces 8.73 (metric tonnes) contributed 14.0 per cent globally, ranks first in production followed by Nigeria (6.9 metric tonnes), India (5.27 metric tonnes), Brazil (5.0 metric tonnes) and Mexico (4.2 metric tonnes) which has 11.0, 8.0, 8.00 and 7.0 per cent share respectively. Ethiopia produces 4.1 metric tonnes contributing 7.0 per cent share globally. It ranks sixth in production next to Brazil. (Source: United States Department of Agriculture, 2024-25).

The area, production and yield of kharif sorghum 2024-25 in India was 14.21 lakh hectare, 17.13 lakh tonnes and 1071 kg/ha, respectively. Area, production and yield of rabi sorghum in India was 25.14 lakh hectare, 30.86 Lakh tonnes and 1086 kg/ha, respectively. (Source: Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Govt. of India, 2024-25)

Among the states, the Maharashtra stood first in area, production and yield of rabi sorghum in (2024-25) was 15.46 lakh hectare, 17.13 lakh tones and 1108.32 kg/ha, respectively. The major sorghum growing states in 2024-25 was Karnataka, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu with production 7.06, 5.27, 4.62, 2.93 and 2.83 lakh tonnes, respectively. (Source: Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Govt. of India, 2024-25)

In Amravati the area, production and productivity of kharif sorghum in (2024-25) was 80.67 hundred hectare, 74.94 hundred tonnes, 928.95 kg/ha, respectively. The area, production and productivity of rabi sorghum in Amravati district (2024-25) was 4.30 hundred hectare, 3.41 tonnes, 793.68 kg/ha, respectively. (Source: Third advance estimates of area, production and productivity, 2024-25)

The Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is a non-parametric, optimization technique widely used for measuring the efficiency of individual decision-making units (DMUs) based on multiple inputs and outputs (Chandrasekhar et al. 2018). It allows for the simultaneous analysis of multiple input and output variables, making it a potent tool for assessing the efficiency of complex systems like agricultural production. DEA offers several advantages over traditional efficiency analysis methods, including the ability to handle multiple inputs and outputs simultaneously, accommodate various forms of production functions, and identify best practices or benchmarks for inefficient units to emulate (Cooper et al. 2006).

It helps in identifying efficient and inefficient farmers and provides insights into how resources can be optimally allocated to improve productivity. The integration of cost analysis with DEA offers a comprehensive assessment of the economic performance of rabi sorghum cultivation in the Amravati district.

Methodology**Study Area**

The study was conducted in the Amravati district of Maharashtra state for the year 2024-25. The district was selected purposely based on the performance of rabi sorghum production. In all, a total of fourteen tehsils are present in the Amravati district out of which three tehsils namely Dharni, Chikhaldara and Dhamangaon Rly. and were selected for the study. Two villages from each tehsil were selected randomly. From each village, twenty farmers were selected randomly. Thus, a total of six villages and one-twenty farmers were selected purposively for assessing the economics and efficiencies of rabi sorghum.

Data analysis Methods**Cost and Returns of Rabi Sorghum**

The cost and returns of Rabi Sorghum cultivation were calculated using standard cost concepts: Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃. Cost A₁ is the sum of all items which include.

Measure of Efficiency of Rabi Sorghum Production

The technical, economic, and allocative efficiency was estimated using the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) Approach. The non-parametric approach constructs linear piecewise functions from empirical observations of input and output without assuming any apriori functional relationship between them (Nair et al. 2012).

Technical Efficiency**Input-Oriented DEA Model**

With Constant Returns to Scale:

Technical efficiency has been estimated as the ratio of the sum of weighted outputs to the sum of weighted inputs (Cooper et al., 2006) The primal of the model has been presented below:

$$\text{Max. } e_{j_0} = \sum_{p=1}^q u_p y_{p_{j_0}}$$

Subject to,

$$\sum_{i=1}^m v_i X_{i_{j_0}} = 1$$

$$\sum_{p=1}^q u_p y_{p_j} - \sum_{i=1}^m v_i X_{i_j} \leq 0$$

Where, $u_p, v_i \geq \epsilon$

i = number of inputs (1 to 6)

(hired human labour, total bullock labour, total machine labour, seed, fertilizer, and family labour)

p = number of outputs (only one output in present study)

j = number of farms (1 to 120)
 X_{i_j0} = vector of level of the i^{th} input being used by the farm '0'
 X_{i_j} = level of use of i^{th} input on j^{th} farm
 V_i = weight attached to input 'i'
 u_p = weight attached to output 'p'
 y_{p_j} = quantity of output 'p' for unit 'j'
 e_{j0} = efficiency score

To solve the above LP problem, it has been converted to its duality as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min. } e_{j0} &= \theta_0 \\ \text{Subject to,} \\ -y_{p_0} + \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j y_{p_j} &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\theta_0 x_{i_{j0}} - \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j x_{i_j} \geq 0$$

Where, $\lambda_j \geq 0; x_{i_j} \geq 0; y_{p_j} \geq 0$

θ = technical efficiency of farm '0'
 λ_j = weights in LP analysis
 $x_{i_j}, y_{p_j} \geq 0$

With Variable Return to Scale:

Pure technical or physical efficiency has been estimated through input oriented VRS model as proposed by Banker, Charnes, and Cooper; 1978; known as the BCC model, and has been resented below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min. } e_{j0} &= \theta_0 \\ \text{Subject to,} \\ -y_{p_0} + \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j y_{p_j} &\geq 0 \\ \theta_0 x_{i_{j0}} - \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j x_{i_j} &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j = 1$$

$$\lambda_j \geq 0; x_{i_j} \geq 0; y_{p_j} \geq 0$$

The model is similar to CCR except that the sum of weights is assumed to be equal to one, which is nothing but the convexity constraint for specifying the model as varying return to scale (VRS)

Allocative Efficiency

The allocative efficiency signifies the use of inputs in the correct proportions reflecting their marginal costs. It focuses on the ability of an economic unit to minimize the cost of production for a given set of input prices by substituting or reallocating inputs and is defined as the

ratio of economic efficiency (cost efficiency) to technical efficiency. The economic efficiency has been estimated by employing cost-minimization Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) and using the prices of inputs. The linear programming form of this model has been presented below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min. } \theta_{i_0} C_{i_0} \\ \text{Subject to,} \\ -y_{p_0} + \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j y_{p_j} &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\theta_{i_0} - \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j x_{i_j} \geq 0$$

$$\lambda_j \geq 0$$

Where,

θ_{i_0} = cost minimizing vector of input quantities for farm '0'

C_{i_0} = vector of input prices for farm '0'

Economic Efficiency

The economic efficiency has been calculated as the ratio of minimum cost to observed cost, mentioned below:

$$EE = \frac{C_{i_0} \theta_{i_0}}{C_{i_0} x_{i_0}}$$

Where,

C_{i_0} = vector of input prices for farm '0'

θ_{i_0} = cost minimizing vector of input quantities for farm '0'

The DEAP Version 2.1 of "The University of New England" was used to estimate technical, allocative, and economic efficiencies by conducting Data Envelopment Analysis.

Results and Discussions

Table 1. presents the distribution of farmer in three categories i.e., small, medium and large according to their size of holding. Out of 120 farmers selected 66.67 percent, 26.67 percent, 11.67 percent belong to small, medium and large size respectively.

From the table 1. it is observed that the average size of land holding for small, medium and large farmers was 1.28, 2.48, 4.40 ha respectively. At the overall level the average size of land holding was 1.91 ha.

Table 1. Distribution of farmers according size of land holding

Sr. No.	Size of holding (Ha)	No. of farmers selected	Average size of Land holding (ha)
1	Small (0.01 ha to 2.00 Ha)	80 (66.67)	1.28
2	Medium (2.01 ha to 4.00 Ha)	26 (26.67)	2.48
3	Large (4.01 ha & above)	14 (11.67)	4.40
	Total	120 (100.00)	1.91

(Figures in parentheses indicates percentages to total farmers)

Cost and Returns of Rabi Sorghum Cultivation

The cost of cultivation is helpful for crop planning therefore in order to know the cost and profitability, the cost of cultivation of turmeric for small, medium and large farmer was workout.

Table 2. Cost and Returns of Small Farmers

Table 2. Cost and Returns of Small Farmers							
Sr. No.	Item		Unit	Inputs/ha.	Rate	Total Cost/ha.	% to Cost C3
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	10.64	321	3415.44	7.07
		Female	Days	17.42	258.75	4507.35	9.33

Per hectare Cost and Returns for Small Farmers

The per hectare cost of cultivation of Rabi Sorghum for small farmers was worked out and presented in table 2.

(Rs./ha)

2	Bullock Labour	Hired	Days	1.47	800.32	1176.47	2.44
		Owned	Days	0.56	752.8	421.57	0.87
3	Machine Labour	Hired	Hours	10.23	808.1	8266.9	17.12
		Owned	Hours	0.88	883.22	777.23	1.61
4	Seed		Kilograms	7.9	329.06	2586.4	5.36
5	Manure		Tonnes	1.41	1714.06	2415.11	5.00
6	Fertilizer		Kilograms	172.7	17.74	3062.92	6.34
8	Herbicide		Rs.	-	-	398.55	0.83
9	Plant protection		Rs.	-	-	898.70	1.86
10	Repairing Charge		Rs.	-	-	228.41	0.47
11	Working Capital		Rs.	-	-	28155.05	58.31
12	Interest on Working Capital		Rs.	-	-	1689.30	3.50
13	Depreciation		Rs.	-	-	586.12	1.21
14	Land Revenue		Rs.	-	-	53.03	0.11
15	Cost A1		Rs.			30483.50	63.13
16	Rent Paid for Leased Land		Rs.	-	-	0.00	0.00
17	Cost A2		Rs.			30483.50	63.13
18	Interest on Fixed Capital		Rs.	-	-	1147.81	2.38
19	Cost B1		Rs.			31631.31	65.51
20	Rental Value of Land		Rs.	-	-	9775.44	20.25
21	Cost B2		Rs.			41406.75	85.75
22	Family Labour	Male	Days	5.02	325.66	1634.80	3.39
		Female	Days	2.62	262.4	687.50	1.42
23	Cost C1		Rs.			33953.61	70.32
24	Cost C2		Rs.			43729.05	90.56
25	Managerial Cost		Rs.	-	-	4556.20	9.44
26	Cost C3		Rs.			48285.25	100.00
27	Yield	Main Produce	Quintals	18.45	2874.08	53026.81	
		By Produce	Quintals	27.50	216.15	5944.01	
28	Gross Value		Rs.			58970.82	
29	Per Quintal Cost of Production		Rs.			2294.92	

It is revealed that the per hectare cost of cultivation of Sorghum at 'Cost A₁' and 'Cost A₂' was Rs **30483.50** whereas 'Cost B₁' was Rs. **31631.31** and 'Cost B₂' was Rs. **41406.75**. whereas 'Cost C₁' was Rs. **33953.61** 'Cost C₂' was Rs. **43729.05** and 'Cost C₃' was Rs. **48285.25** In 'Cost A₁' share of was 63.13 per cent, hired human labour was 16.4 per cent, hired machine labour was 18.73 per cent, and manure was 5 per cent. All these inputs are cash inputs for which farmers are required to pay immediately from his pocket.

Cost B₁' contributes to 65.51 per cent, and 'Cost B₂' contribute 85.75 per cent. The share of family labour was 4.81 per cent. The per hectare yield obtained by small farmers was 18.45 quintal with a gross return of Rs. **58970.82**. In this case, the per quintal cost of production was Rs. **2294.92**

Per hectare Cost and Returns for Medium Farmers

The per hectare cost of cultivation of Rabi Sorghum for medium farmers was worked out and presented in Table 3.

(Rs./ha)

Table 3. Cost and Returns of Medium Farmers

Table 3. Cost and Returns of Medium Farmers							
Sr. No.	Item	Unit	Inputs/ha.	Rate	Total Cost/ha.	% to Cost C3	
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	12.5	361.97	4524.67	8.12
		Female	Days	22.6	280.8	6346.15	11.39
2	Bullock Labour	Hired	Days	1.25	778.11	971.08	1.74
		Owned	Days	0.58	777.24	450.8	0.81
3	Machine Labour	Hired	Hours	8.93	788.95	7045.33	12.64
		Owned	Hours	3.93	825.66	3244.85	5.82
4	Seed	Kilograms	8.0	364.61	2913.2	5.23	
5	Manure	Tonnes	1.16	1636.57	1896.78	3.40	
6	Fertilizer	Kilograms	181.7	16.79	3051.82	5.48	
8	Herbicide	Rs.	-	-	400.43	0.72	
9	Plant protection	Rs.	-	-	976.06	1.75	
10	Repairing Charge	Rs.	-	-	225.24	0.40	
11	Working Capital	Rs.	-	-	32046.41	57.50	
12	Interest on Working Capital	Rs.	-	-	1922.78	3.45	
13	Depreciation	Rs.	-	-	603.50	1.08	
14	Land Revenue	Rs.	-	-	58.00	0.10	
15	Cost A1	Rs.			34630.69	62.14	
16	Rent Paid for Leased Land	Rs.	-	-	0.00	0.00	

17	Cost A2		Rs.			34630.69	62.14
18	Interest on Fixed Capital		Rs.	-	-	2334.58	4.19
19	Cost B1		Rs.			36965.28	66.33
20	Rental Value of Land		Rs.	-	-	11074.86	19.87
21	Cost B2		Rs.			48040.14	86.20
22	Family Labour	Male	Days	5.19	358.65	1861.39	3.34
		Female	Days	2.72	280.14	761.97	1.37
23	Cost C1		Rs.			39588.64	71.04
24	Cost C2		Rs.			50663.50	90.91
25	Managerial Cost		Rs.	-	-	5066.35	9.09
26	Cost C3		Rs.			55729.85	100.00
27	Yield	Main Produce	Quintals	21.17	2878.69	60941.80	
		By Produce	Quintals	26.32	222.47	5855.37	
28	Gross Value		Rs.			66797.17	
29	Per Quintal Cost of Production		Rs.			2355.90	

It is revealed that the per hectare cost of cultivation of Sorghum at 'Cost A₁' and 'Cost A₂' was Rs. **34630.69** whereas 'Cost B₁' was Rs. **36965.28** and 'Cost B₂' was Rs. **48040.14** whereas 'Cost C₁' was Rs. **39588.64**, 'Cost C₂' was Rs. **50663.50** and 'Cost C₃' was Rs. **55729.85**. In 'Cost A₁' share of was 62.14 per cent, hired human labour was 19.51 per cent, hired machine labour was 18.46 per cent and manure was 3.40 per cent. All these inputs are cash inputs for which farmers are required to pay immediately from his pocket.

'Cost B₁' contributes to 61.68 per cent, and 'Cost B₂' contributes 86.20 per cent. The share of family labour was 4.71 per cent. The per hectare yield obtained by medium farmers was 21.17 quintal with a gross return of Rs. **66797.17** In this case, the per quintal cost of production was Rs. **2355.90**

Per hectare Cost and Returns for Large Farmers

The per hectare cost of cultivation Rabi Sorghum for large farmers was worked out and presented in Table 4.

(Rs./ha)

Table 4: Cost and Returns of Large Farmers

Table 4. Cost and Returns of Large Farmers							
Sr. No.	Item		Unit	Inputs/ha.	Rate	Total Cost/ha.	% to Cost C3
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	13.32	372.89	4966.89	8.58
		Female	Days	23.29	280.15	6524.8	11.27
2	Bullock Labour	Hired	Days	0.83	821.04	681.46	1.18
		Owned	Days	0.73	847.42	618.62	1.07
3	Machine Labour	Hired	Hours	10.37	826.28	8568.5	14.80
		Owned	Hours	2.82	838.89	2365.66	4.09
4	Seed		Kilograms	7.30	418.81	3057.28	5.28
5	Manure		Tonnes	1.17	1826.36	2136.84	3.69
6	Fertilizer		Kilograms	184.5	17.95	3311.52	5.72
8	Herbicide		Rs.	-	-	159.60	0.28
9	Plant protection		Rs.	-	-	1000.25	1.73
10	Repairing Charge		Rs.	-	-	228.31	0.39
11	Working Capital		Rs.	-	-	33619.73	58.07
12	Interest on Working Capital		Rs.	-	-	2017.18	3.48
13	Depreciation		Rs.	-	-	560.94	0.97
14	Land Revenue		Rs.	-	-	54.97	0.09
15	Cost A1		Rs.			36252.82	62.62
16	Rent Paid for Leased Land		Rs.	-	-	0.00	0.00
17	Cost A2		Rs.			36252.82	62.62
18	Interest on Fixed Capital		Rs.	-	-	2668.57	4.61
19	Cost B1		Rs.			38921.39	67.22
20	Rental Value of Land		Rs.	-	-	11410.24	19.71
21	Cost B2		Rs.			50331.63	86.93
22	Family Labour	Male	Days	4.79	347.77	1665.82	2.88
		Female	Days	2.55	249.72	636.78	1.10
23	Cost C1		Rs.			41223.99	71.20
24	Cost C2		Rs.			52634.23	90.91
25	Managerial Cost		Rs.	-	-	5263.42	9.09
26	Cost C3		Rs.			57897.65	100.00
27	Yield	Main Produce	Quintals	20.58	3046.84	62703.98	
		By Produce	Quintals	26.07	233.5	6087.25	
28	Gross Value		Rs.			68791.23	
29	Per Quintal Cost of Production		Rs.			2517.51	

It is revealed that the per hectare cost of cultivation of Sorghum at 'Cost A₁' and 'Cost A₂' was Rs. **36252.82** whereas 'Cost B₁' was Rs. **38921.39** and 'Cost B₂' was Rs. **50331.63**. whereas 'Cost C₁' was Rs. **41223.99**, 'Cost C₂' was Rs. **52634.23** and 'Cost C₃' was Rs. **57897.65**. In 'Cost A₁' share was 62.62 per cent, hired human labour was 19.85 per cent, hired machine labour was 18.89 per cent and manure was 3.69 per cent and hired. All these inputs are cash inputs for which farmers are required to pay immediately from his pocket.

'Cost B₁' contributes to 67.22 per cent, and 'Cost B₂' contributes 86.93 per cent. The share of family labour was 3.98 per cent. The per hectare yield obtained by large farmers was 20.58 quintal with a gross return of Rs. **68791.23** In this case, the per quintal cost of production was Rs. **2517.51**.

Cost and Returns for Overall Farmers

The per hectare cost of cultivation of Rabi sorghum for overall farmers was worked out and presented in table 5.

It is revealed that the per hectare cost of cultivation of Sorghum at 'Cost A₁' and 'Cost A₂' was Rs. **33386.17**. whereas 'Cost B₁' was Rs. **35541.42** and 'Cost B₂' was Rs. **45846.89**. whereas 'Cost C₁' was Rs. **38015.51**, 'Cost C₂' was Rs. **48320.98** and 'Cost C₃' was Rs. **53153.08**. In 'Cost A₁' share was 62.81 per cent, hired human labour was 18.32 per cent, manure was 4.13 per cent and hired machine labour was 18.73 per cent. All these inputs are cash inputs for which farmers are required to pay immediately from his pocket.

Table 5. Cost and Returns of Overall Farmers

(Rs./ha)

Sr. No.	Item	Unit	Inputs/ha.	Rate	Total Cost/ha.	% to Cost C3	
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	11.88	348.17	4136.26	7.78
		Female	Days	20.56	272.52	5603.04	10.54
2	Bullock Labour	Hired	Days	1.24	799.09	990.87	1.86
		Owned	Days	0.63	777.37	489.74	0.92
3	Machine Labour	Hired	Hours	10.00	806.82	8068.24	15.18
		Owned	Hours	2.24	842.41	1887	3.55
4	Seed	Kilograms	7.8	365	2843.38	5.35	
5	Manure	Tonnes	1.26	1740.75	2193.34	4.13	
6	Fertilizer	Kilograms	177.2	17.69	3134.93	5.90	
8	Herbicide	Rs.	-	-	347.92	0.65	
9	Plant protection	Rs.	-	-	958.94	1.80	
10	Repairing Charge	Rs.	-	-	230.00	0.43	
11	Working Capital	Rs.	-	-	30883.66	58.10	
12	Interest on Working Capital	Rs.	-	-	1853.02	3.49	
13	Depreciation	Rs.	-	-	593.62	1.12	
14	Land Revenue	Rs.	-	-	55.87	0.11	
15	Cost A1	Rs.			33386.17	62.81	
16	Rent Paid for Leased Land	Rs.	-	-	0.00	0.00	
17	Cost A2	Rs.			33386.17	62.81	
18	Interest on Fixed Capital	Rs.	-	-	2155.25	4.05	
19	Cost B1	Rs.			35541.42	66.87	
20	Rental Value of Land	Rs.	-	-	10305.47	19.39	
21	Cost B2	Rs.			45846.89	86.25	
22	Family Labour	Male	Days	5.09	342.26	1742.11	3.28
		Female	Days	2.68	273.13	731.98	1.38
23	Cost C1	Rs.			38015.51	71.52	
24	Cost C2	Rs.			48320.98	90.91	
25	Managerial Cost	Rs.	-	-	4832.10	9.09	
26	Cost C3	Rs.			53153.08	100.00	
27	Yield	Main Produce	Quintals	19.50	2882.28	56204.53	
		By Produce	Quintals	26.85	222.1	5963.50	
28	Gross Value	Rs.			62168.03		
29	Per Quintal Cost of Production	Rs.			2419.98		

'Cost B₁' contributes to 66.87 per cent, and 'Cost B₂' contributes 86.25 per cent. The share of family labour was 3.98 per cent. The per hectare yield obtained by overall farmers was 19.50 quintal with a gross return of Rs. **62168.03**. In this case, the per quintal cost of production was Rs. **2419.98**.

Per ha Cost and Return of Sorghum Cultivation

The data on cost and returns from Sorghum is presented in the table 6. It was observed from the data that the gross return from Sorghum production for the overall size group was Rs. 62168.03 per hectare. The gross return in the small size group was Rs. 58970.82, in the medium

size group was Rs. 66797.17, in the large size group was Rs.68791.23. The total cost at 'Cost A₁', 'Cost A₂', 'Cost B₁', 'Cost B₂', 'Cost C₁', 'Cost C₂', and 'Cost C₃' for overall farmers was Rs. 33386.17, Rs. 35541.42, Rs. 45846.89, Rs. 45846.89, Rs. 48320.98 and Rs. 53153.08 respectively.

Profit at 'Cost A₁' for the overall size group from Sorghum cultivation was Rs. 28781.86 at 'Cost A₂' was Rs. 28781.86, at 'Cost B₁' Rs. 26626.61, at 'Cost B₂' was Rs. 16321.14 at 'Cost C₁' was Rs. 24152.52, at 'Cost C₂' was Rs. 13847.05, and at 'Cost C₃' was Rs. 9014.95

Per Hectare Cost and Returns from Sorghum Cultivation.

Table 6. Per Hectare Cost and Returns from Sorghum

Sr. No.	Particulars	Size of Holding			Overall
		Small	Medium	Large	
1	Main Produce	18.45	21.17	20.58	19.50

	Price	2874.08	2878.69	3046.84	2882.28
	Value of Main Produce	53026.81	60941.80	62703.98	56204.53
2	By Produce	27.50	26.32	26.07	26.85
	Price	216.15	222.47	233.50	222.10
	Value of By Produce	5944.01	5855.37	6087.25	5963.50
3	Value of Total Produce	58970.82	66797.17	68791.23	62168.03
4	Total Cost				
	Cost A1	30483.50	34630.69	36252.82	33386.17
	Cost A2	30483.50	34630.69	36252.82	33386.17
	Cost B1	31631.31	36965.28	38921.39	35541.42
	Cost B2	41406.75	48040.14	50331.63	45846.89
	Cost C1	33953.61	39588.64	41223.99	45846.89
	Cost C2	43729.05	50663.50	52634.23	48320.98
	Cost C3	48285.25	55729.85	57897.65	53153.08
5	Net Return Over				
	Cost A1	28487.32	32166.48	32538.41	28781.86
	Cost A2	28487.32	32166.48	32538.41	28781.86
	Cost B1	27339.51	29831.89	29869.84	26626.61
	Cost B2	17564.07	18757.03	18459.60	16321.14
	Cost C1	25017.21	27208.53	27567.24	24152.52
	Cost C2	15241.77	16133.67	16157.00	13847.05
	Cost C3	10685.57	11067.32	10893.58	9014.95

Input-Output Relationship

The input-output ratio at the overall level i.e. at Cost 'A₁', 'A₂', 'B₁', 'B₂', 'C₁', 'C₂', and 'C₃' was 1.86,1.86,1.75,1.36,1.64 1.29, and 1.17 respectively. The input-output ratio in small size farmers at 'Cost A₁' was 1.93, 'Cost A₂' was 1.93, at 'Cost B₁' was 1.86, at 'Cost B₂' was 1.42, at 'Cost C₁' was 1.74, at 'Cost C₂' was 1.35, and at 'Cost C₃' was 1.22. The input-output ratio in medium size farmers at 'Cost A₁' was

1.93, 'Cost A₂' was 1.93, at 'Cost B₁' was 1.81, at 'Cost B₂' was 1.39, at 'Cost C₁' was 1.69, at 'Cost C₂' was 1.32 and at 'Cost C₃' was 1.20. The input-output ratio in large size group farmers at 'Cost A₁' was 1.9, 'Cost A₂' was 1.9, at 'Cost B₁' was 1.77, at 'Cost B₂' was 1.37 at 'Cost C₁' was 1.67, at 'Cost C₂' was 1.31, and at 'Cost C₃' was 1.19. The results showed that turmeric is a more profitable crop to large farmers followed by medium farmers.

Table 7. Input-Output Relationship of Sorghum Cultivation

Sr. No.	Particulars	Size of Holding			
		Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	A1	1.93	1.93	1.9	1.86
2	A2	1.93	1.93	1.9	1.86
3	B1	1.86	1.81	1.77	1.75
4	B2	1.42	1.39	1.37	1.36
5	C1	1.74	1.69	1.67	1.64
6	C2	1.35	1.32	1.31	1.29
7	C3	1.22	1.20	1.19	1.17

Technical, Economic, and Allocative Efficiency of Rabi Sorghum Production

The results of sorghum's technical, economic, and allocative efficiency were determined using the data envelopment analysis approach. The technical efficiency was calculated based on the input-oriented DEA model.

1. Input-Oriented Technical Efficiency of Sorghum Production

The table 8. presents an analysis of the input-oriented technical efficiency of Sorghum production under both Constant Returns to Scale (CRS) and Variable Returns to Scale (VRS) models.

Table 8. Input-Oriented Technical Efficiency of Sorghum Production

Efficiency Score	Input-Oriented			
	CRS		VRS	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
0.401-0.500	1	0.83	0	0
0.501-0.600	6	5.00	9	7.50
0.601-0.700	25	20.83	17	14.20
0.701-0.800	39	32.50	23	19.00
0.801-0.900	26	21.66	29	24.00
0.901-0.999	22	18.33	37	30.30
1	1	0.83	6	5.00
Total	120	100	120	100
Mean	0.760		0.874	
Minimum	0.471		0.523	

Maximum	1	1
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Under CRS assumptions, the mean input-oriented technical efficiency of sorghum farmers is 0.760, indicating that, on average, farmers could reduce their input use by about 24% without affecting output. Most farmers (32.50%) fall in the 0.701–0.800 efficiency range, followed by 21.66% in 0.801–0.900 and 20.83% in 0.601–0.700, showing that the majority operate at moderate to high efficiency. Only 1 farmer (0.83%) reached full efficiency (score 1) and only 0.83% scored below 0.500, suggesting that extreme inefficiency is rare. The minimum efficiency of 0.471 and maximum of 1.0 further highlight variability among farmers in the effective use of inputs.

Under VRS model, the mean efficiency increases to 0.874, indicating that farmers are closer to the efficiency frontier once farm size is

accounted for. The largest proportion of farmers (30.3%) are in the 0.901–0.999 range, followed by 24% in 0.801–0.900 and 19% in 0.701–0.800, showing that most farmers are highly efficient. Six farmers (5%) achieved full efficiency, and the minimum efficiency is 0.523, higher than under CRS. This suggests that a substantial portion of inefficiency under CRS is due to scale inefficiency, and optimizing farm size along with better input management can further enhance overall technical efficiency.

Output-Oriented Technical Efficiency of Sorghum Production

The table 9. presents an analysis of the output-oriented technical efficiency of Sorghum production under both Constant Returns to Scale (CRS) and Variable Returns to Scale (VRS) models.

Table 9: Output-Oriented Technical Efficiency of Sorghum Production

Efficiency Score	Output-Oriented			
	CRS		VRS	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
0.401-0.500	1	0.83	0	0
0.501-0.600	6	5	2	1.60
0.601-0.700	25	20.83	13	10.80
0.701-0.800	39	32.5	21	17.50
0.801-0.900	26	21.66	24	20.00
0.901-0.999	22	18.33	49	40.83
1	1	0.83	11	9.16
Total	120	100	120	100
Mean	0.760		0.932	
Minimum	0.471		0.584	
Maximum	1		1	

Under CRS assumptions, the mean input-oriented technical efficiency of sorghum farmers is 0.760, indicating that, on average, farmers could reduce their input use by about 24% without affecting output. Most farmers (32.5%) fall in the 0.701–0.800 efficiency range, followed by 21.66% in 0.801–0.900 and 20.83% in 0.601–0.700, showing that the majority operate at moderate to high efficiency. Only 1 farmer (0.83%) reached full efficiency (score 1) and only 0.83% scored below 0.500, suggesting that extreme inefficiency is rare. The minimum efficiency of 0.471 and maximum of 1.0 further highlight variability among farmers in the effective use of inputs.

Under VRS model, the mean output-oriented technical efficiency of sorghum farmers is 0.932, indicating that, on average, farmers could increase their output by about 6.8% without using additional inputs.

The largest proportion of farmers (40.83%) are in the 0.901–0.999 efficiency range, followed by 20% in 0.801–0.900 and 17.5% in 0.701–0.800, showing that most farmers are highly efficient in converting inputs into maximum possible output. Eleven farmers (9.16%) achieved full efficiency (score 1), while the minimum efficiency is 0.584, higher than under CRS. This suggests that when scale effects are accounted for, sorghum farmers are generally operating close to the efficiency frontier, and further improvements in output can be achieved primarily through better management and optimization of farm practices rather than additional inputs.

Allocative and Economic Efficiency of Sorghum Production
The Table 10. illustrated the allocative and economic efficiency of Sorghum production.

Table 10: Allocative and Economic Efficiency of Sorghum Production

Efficiency Score	Allocative Efficiency		Economic Efficiency	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
0.201-0.300	0	0	3	2.50
0.301-0.400	9	7.50	16	13.33
0.401-0.500	35	29.17	33	27.50
0.501-0.600	18	15.00	18	15.00
0.601-0.700	18	15.00	16	13.33
0.701-0.800	11	9.17	5	4.17
0.801-0.900	13	10.83	23	19.17
0.901-0.999	16	13.33	6	5.00
1	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	120	100.00	120	100.00
Mean	0.625		0.588	
Minimum	0.302		0.260	
Maximum	0.963		0.962	

In terms of allocative efficiency, the majority of sorghum producers (29.17%) achieved scores in the 0.401–0.500 range, while another 30.00% were distributed across the 0.501–0.700 range, suggesting that most farmers were moderately efficient in resource allocation. A substantial proportion (24.16%) also attained higher efficiency levels above 0.801, indicating that nearly one-fourth of the farmers were close to optimal use of inputs. Only 7.50% of producers recorded low efficiency levels below 0.401, reflecting that very few farmers struggled with input allocation. The mean allocative efficiency score of 0.625, with values ranging from 0.302 to 0.963, highlights a generally satisfactory level of input use efficiency among sorghum growers.

Regarding economic efficiency, the distribution shows relatively weaker performance compared to allocative efficiency. The largest

proportion of farmers (27.50%) fell within the 0.401–0.500 range, followed by 15.00% in the 0.501–0.600 category and 13.33% each in the 0.301–0.400 and 0.601–0.700 ranges. Although a significant share (24.17%) achieved efficiency levels above 0.801, a noticeable number of farmers (15.83%) operated below 0.400, indicating cost and profitability constraints. The mean score of 0.588, with a minimum of 0.260 and a maximum of 0.962, suggests that while some farmers operate close to full efficiency, others face challenges in converting resources into maximum possible profit.

Factors Affecting Technical Efficiency of Sorghum Production

The factors (like age, educational qualification, family size, area, and irrigation facility) affecting the technical efficiency of soybean production has been studied in this section.

The Table 11. presents factors affecting the technical efficiency of Sorghum production.

Age	Educational Qualification	Family Size	Area	Irrigation Facility	R ²
0.0118	0.0236	0.0079	0.0382*	0.0317	0.0761

(***, **, and * indicate significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels respectively)

The factors (such as age, educational qualification, family size, area, and irrigation facility) affecting the technical efficiency of sorghum production have been analyzed in this section.

The analysis revealed limited explanatory power, with an R² value of 0.0721, indicating that only 7.61% of the variation in technical efficiency was explained by the independent variables.

The factor 'age' had a positive coefficient of 0.0118, though statistically non-significant. 'Educational qualification' also showed a positive effect (0.0236) but was not significant. 'Family size' had a coefficient of 0.0079, indicating a minor positive influence. The 'area' under cultivation had a coefficient of 0.0382, which was statistically significant at the 10% level. The 'irrigation facility' had a coefficient of 0.0317, showing a positive but non-significant effect.

Conclusions.

The study highlights the pivotal role of economic and resource use efficiency in enhancing the profitability and sustainability of rabi sorghum cultivation in the Amravati district. The findings revealed that although many farmers achieved moderate levels of technical efficiency, allocative and economic efficiencies remained comparatively lower, indicating suboptimal utilization of available resources. Medium farmers performed better in terms of cost management and profitability, suggesting that farm size and management practices significantly influence overall efficiency. The analysis also showed that human labour, machine labour, and fertilizers were the major cost components contributing to production variability. Therefore, improving input-use efficiency through timely availability of quality seeds, fertilizers, and mechanization support is essential. Policy initiatives focusing on strengthening extension services, promoting awareness of improved production technologies, and facilitating access to institutional credit can further enhance farm-level performance. By adopting efficient resource management practices and bridging the existing efficiency gaps, farmers can significantly improve productivity and income from rabi sorghum. The study underscores the importance of continuous monitoring, technological interventions, and farmer-oriented policies to achieve sustainable growth and economic viability of rabi sorghum cultivation in the region.

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